

Supplemental material:

Adsorption Selectivity of Water-Ethanol Mixtures on Organosilica Surfaces: Role of Hydrophilicity

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Contact angle measurement

Contact angle measurements were performed using a protocol similar to the one described by Shi et al. [45]. Water droplets, composed of 2000 water molecules, were placed on a solid surface with lateral dimensions of $10 \times 10 \text{ nm}^2$. The system was equilibrated at a temperature of 300 K, and the density was recorded for 2 ns. The contact angle was estimated by fitting a straight line to the density profile at $z \rightarrow 0$. Examples of density profiles are shown in Fig. S1.

Interface thickness measurement

The typical thickness of a given fluid layer was defined by its variance σ_i . In the case of the ethanol density layer ‘i’ with density profile $\rho_i^{\text{eth}}(z)$, the variance is defined as

$$\sigma_i^{\text{eth}} = \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} z^2 \rho_i^{\text{eth}}(z) dz}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \rho_i^{\text{eth}}(z) dz} - (\mu_i^{\text{eth}})^2, \quad (\text{S1})$$

where μ_i^{eth} is the mean position of the ethanol density layer ‘i’. Using a similar expression for the water density layer, σ_i^{wat} , we defined the average variance σ_i of the density layer ‘i’ as

$$\sigma_i = \frac{m_i^{\text{eth}} \sigma_i^{\text{eth}} + m_i^{\text{wat}} \sigma_i^{\text{wat}}}{m_i^{\text{eth}} + m_i^{\text{wat}}}, \quad (\text{S2})$$

where m_i^{eth} and m_i^{wat} are the masses per surface unit of ethanol and water, respectively, within the density layer 'i'.

Hydrogen bonds analysis

Hydrogen bonds analysis was performed using MDAnalysis [42]. Hydrogen bonds were identified based on the following geometric criteria:

- A maximum donor-hydrogen distance of 1.2 Å.
- A maximum donor-acceptor distance of 3.4 Å, as determined from the radial distribution functions.
- A minimum donor-hydrogen-acceptor angle of 150 °.

The final metric, N_{HB} , is obtained by summing-up all the contributions from the different hydrogen bonds for each molecule, including both hydrogen bonds that are given and accepted.

Neighboring ethanol carbon-carbon analysis

The number of neighboring ethanol carbons per carbon atom, $N_{\text{C-C}}$, was determined by summing the neighboring carbon atoms j located within a radius of 4.6 Å of a given carbon atom i . Only carbon atoms from different ethanol molecules were included in this calculation.

Figure S1: Density profiles used for contact angle measurements, with yellow indicating high atomic density and blue indicating zero density. The systems are water droplets made of 2000 molecules on a Q^3 silica surface. The surface is located at $z < 0$. Profiles are shown for three cases: $r_{\text{C/O}} = 1.0$ with measured contact angle of approximately 90° (see the red dashed line), $r_{\text{C/O}} = 0.5$ with contact angle 60°, and $r_{\text{C/O}} = 0.0$ with contact angle 40°.

Figure S2: Density profiles next to the interface for the fluid, $\rho^{\text{tot}} = \rho^{\text{eth}} + \rho^{\text{wat}}$. The position $z = 0$ corresponds to the Gibbs dividing plane, and the bulk ethanol mass fraction far from the solid surface is $r_{\text{bulk}}^{\text{eth}} \approx 0.12$. The results were obtained with Q³ organosilica surfaces $r_{C/O} = 1$ corresponding to a hydrophobic surface (full blue line), and $r_{C/O} = 0$ corresponding to a hydrophilic pure silica surface (full red line). The dashed dark line was obtained with graphite, and the dotted dark line with a liquid-vapor interface.

Figure S3: Density profiles next to the interface, for respectively the ethanol ρ^{eth} (A), the water ρ^{wat} (B), and the fluid $\rho^{\text{tot}} = \rho^{\text{eth}} + \rho^{\text{wat}}$ (C). The results were obtained with Q³ organosilica surfaces with $r_{C/O} = 1$. The position $z = 0$ corresponds to the Gibbs dividing plane, and the ethanol mass fraction is $r_{\text{total}}^{\text{eth}} \approx 0.12$. The red area corresponds to the first density layer as detected with the ITIM algorithm of Pytim [40, 41], the yellow area to the second layer, the blue area to the third layer, and the gray area to the fourth layer.

Figure S4: The ethanol enrichment factor, E_2^{eth} , within the second density layer next to the interface. A) E_2^{eth} as a function of the carbon-to-oxygen ratio, $r_{C/O}$, of the organosilica surfaces, from $r_{C/O} = 0$ (hydrophilic surface) to $r_{C/O} = 1$ (hydrophobic surface). The ethanol mass fraction is $r_{\text{total}}^{\text{eth}} = 0.12$. B) E_2^{eth} as a function of the bulk ethanol mass ratio, $r_{\text{bulk}}^{\text{eth}}$, in the case of the hydrophobic surface with $r_{C/O} = 1$ (blue), and hydrophilic surface with $r_{C/O} = 0$ (red).

Figure S5: Density maps of ethanol within the first density layer in the case $r_{C/O} = 1$, with a total ethanol mass fraction $r_{\text{total}}^{\text{eth}} = 0.12$. Yellow indicates a low ethanol mass fraction ($r_1^{\text{eth}} = 0$), while blue indicates a high ethanol mass fraction ($r_1^{\text{eth}} = 1$). The white dots represent the average locations of the $-\text{CH}_3$ groups. Surfaces are Q^2 (A), Q^2/Q^3 (B), Q^3 (C), amorphous (D), Q^3/Q^4 (E), and Q^4 (F).

Figure S6: Ethanol mass fraction within the first density layer [Eq. (2)], r_1^{eth} , as a function of the surface patch area, A_p . A patch is defined as the largest possible ellipse connecting neighbor $-\text{CH}_3$ groups within the (x, y) plan (see examples in Fig. 4 B, C).

Figure S7: A) Number of hydrogen bonds, N_{HB} , per ethanol molecule, between the ethanol and the surface. Blue disks are the default Q^3 surfaces, the square is Q^2 , the pentagone is Q^2/Q^3 , the hexagone is the amorphous surface, the triangle-up is Q^3/Q^4 , and the triangle-right is Q^4 . The gray squares are from graphite surface, and the gray pentagones are from the liquid-vapor interface. B) Number of hydrogen bonds per water molecule, between the water and the surface.

Figure S8: Average number neighboring carbon atoms per carbon atom, $N_{\text{C-C}}$, as a function of the bulk ethanol mass fraction, $r_{\text{bulk}}^{\text{eth}}$. The silica surface is Q^3 with $r_{\text{C/O}} = 1.0$. Filled symbols represent measurements from the first density layer, while open symbols are from the bulk.

Figure S9: First density layer with $r_{\text{bulk}}^{\text{eth}} \approx 0.1$, with the silica surface in gray, the water molecules in red, and ethanol molecules in cyan.

Figure S10: A) Orientation probability distribution for the dipole of the ethanol molecules from the first density layer, $p^{\text{eth}}(\theta)$. Molecules with their dipole parallel to the surface have an angle $\theta = 90^\circ$. All systems have an ethanol mass fraction of $r_{\text{total}}^{\text{eth}} = 0.12$, the blue line represents a Q^3 surface with $r_{C/O} = 1$, the red line represents a Q^3 surface with $r_{C/O} = 0$, the dark dashed represents graphite, and the orange dotted line represents the liquid-vapor interface. B) Orientation probability distribution for the dipole of the water molecules from the first density layer, $p^{\text{wat}}(\theta)$.

Figure S11: Typical width of the first density layer, σ_1 [see Eq. (S2)], as a function of E_1^{eth} for various surfaces: Q^2 with $r_{C/O} = 1$ (blue square), Q^2/Q^3 with $r_{C/O} = 1$ (blue pentagon), amorphous with $r_{C/O} = 1$ (blue hexagon), Q^3 with $r_{C/O} = 1$ (blue disk), Q^3/Q^4 with $r_{C/O} = 1$ (blue upward triangle), Q^4 (blue rightward triangle), graphite (gray square), and vapor (gray pentagon). The dashed line serves as a visual guide.